

***Samaraiccha Kahā* of Ācārya Haribhadra Sūri
(A Brief Study of the Mahārāstri Prakrit text of 8th century)**

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Samaraiccha Kahā is a religious novel by the celebrated Jaina Ācārya Haribhadra Sūri. Written in prose with inserted verses of varying length, usually in *āryā* metre, *Samaraiccha Kahā* is generally ignored but it is a brilliant prakrit text of different and enormous subject matter. The language of *Samaraiccha Kahā* is Jain Mahārāstri (JM). Mahārāstri Prakrit treated in the beginning as *Sāmānyā Prakrit* or *ārsāprākrit*. From the date of Daṇḍin (6th Cen. A.D.) onwards it is named *Mahārāstri* and is thought to be the best *Prākrit* in which famous epics were composed (*Daṇḍin-Kāvyaadarśa* 1.35). The language originated in Maharastra is *Mahārāstri*. *Mahārāstri* was understandable in the bigger middle region of India during this period. The earlier *svetāmbara Jaina ācāryas* like Bhadrabāhu, Kalakācārya, Padalīpta etc. were closely associated with Mahārāstra and specifically Pratisthāna. Nearly for six centuries Sātavāhanas ruled over Mahārāstra who were pro-Prakrit by nature and liberal in religious matters. The various *Niryuktis*, *Bhāṣyas*, *Cūrñis* and the narrative works like *Paumacariya*, *Vāsudevahim̐di* and others may be taken to represent the archaic form of JM in no other Prakrit language than Jain Mahārāstri. In its classical form, as represented by Haribhadra, Uddyotanasūri, Silāṅka and Dhanapāla, it shows influence of Skt. but still maintaining tendencies of colloquial languages in variety of forms and the use of *deśi* words [1]. Such a huge literature is produced in India for such a long period (from 3rd Cen. A.D. up to 15th Cen. A.D.)

Haribhadra and Jain Narrative Literature

Haribhadra is the most celebrated, honoured and versatile author in the 8th Century, acquired the skills in Jain Mahārāstri and produced (i) a huge prose narrative like *Samaraiccha Kahā*, (ii) a unique satirical work like *Dhuttākkhāna* which inspired Skt. *Dharmaparikṣā* and *Apabhraṃsa Dhammaparikkhā* in the later period, (iii) first Jain Mahārāstri book dedicated to *Yoga* in Jaina manner (viz. *Yogasayaya*), (v) other treatises related to Karma theory, Monastic conduct, Layman's conduct, Didactic and *Karaṇānuyoga*. Haribhadra included a lot of folk stories, examples, fables and traditional religious stories in his commentaries on *Āvassaya* and *Dasaveyāliya* [2].

Underlying the main narrative and most of the inserted narratives, in which, after all sorts of adventures the heroes and heroines renounces the world and enter the order, there are the tenets of Jain doctrine, and in the numerous stories, parables and fairy tales inserted we come across many themes which we find often in Indian narrative literature [3].

Objective of *Samarāicccakahā*

In ancient India, how people could eradicate the suffering of *saṃsāra* and obtain liberation (*mokṣa*) was a serious matter. This was also the case for the Jainas. They developed an original theory of *karma* since the time of Mahāvīra. Umāsvāti (c. 1st-2nd century) systematized a theory of liberation in his work, the *Tattvārthasūtra*. Within that text he describes the Jaina view of the world and *karma*. In the 10th chapter he explains in particular the Jaina theory of liberation. Haribhadra Sūri (c. 8th century), a Jaina *Svetāmbara* monk and scholar, also discusses a theory of liberation in the *Anekāntavādapraveśa* [4] and about worldly deeds to be followed in one's life to attain liberation, he wrote in lucid Prakrit language *Samarāicccakahā*, Haribhadra's fame as a creative literary writer rests chiefly on this Prakrit *Samarāicccakahā*, a work which the author himself describes as *dharmakathā* and which Winternitz fittingly terms a

religious novel. The emphasis of this book laid on the theory of karma, transmigration, leading a virtuous life, indifference to worldly pleasures, renunciation, achieving the highest goal of life and so on [5].

Though this book is popularly known as *Samaraiiccakahā* but in B. H. Dosi's edition we see that Haribhadrasūri himself has mentioned its name as *Samarāiccacariya*. The *Samarāiccakahā*, is a *dharmakathā* type work. It seems to be the most popular narrative work. It is composed primary in prose in Jain *Mahārāstrī Prakrit* strewn with forms of *Śaurasent* Prakrit here and there. It is divided into nine sections that narrate the story of nine births of two persons namely Aggisammā & Guṇaseṇa.

Particulars of the Book

The *Samaraiiccha Kahā* brings to light spiritual contribution of Haribhadra to Jainism. He highlights the significance and necessity of observing ethical religious and philosophical tenets of Jainism. On the one hand he endeavours hard to expose the supposed absurdities of Hinduism, and on the other hand he tries to show the superiority and relevance of Jaina religion. This approach clearly bears out his strong bias against Hinduism, chiefly because of the latter's immense popularity.

Overview of the Text

The fortune of the hero Samarāditya is traced through his ninth births (*bhava*). Underlying all the narratives, there is the Jaina doctrine of *karman*. For the study of the cultural religious and economic history of northern India of the eighth century AD, the work offers a unique scope. In the first book there is a reference to the well-known Madana festival. The second provides an interesting description of marriage of those days and mentions a *nāga* temple and also refers to the cloth of *Cina* and *ArdhaCina*. The third book refers to the philosophy of *Cārvāka* and in the fourth we not only have a reference to *Tāmralipta* port but also to *Katahadvipa*, which is also mentioned in the Cola inscriptions and the *Kathāsaritasāgara*. It appears from this book of

Samaraiiccha Kahā that there was brisk commerce between eastern india and the islands of east indies in those days. The fifth book refers to *Suvarṇabhumi* and *Mahākataha*. The sixth contains a wealth of information. Here we have the confirmation of the belief that the God *Skanda* was looked upon as the presiding god of thieves. We are told that *SkandaRudra* was the inventors of thief's pill called *Coraguliya*, which was used as *Paradṛṣṭimohani* (charmmers of others sight). There is also edetailed description of the temple *Kātyāyani*, which had a four armed icon of the goddess with the implements *kodaṇḍa*, *ghantā*, *khadga* and the tail of *Mahiṣāsura*. It further refers to the town of *Devarupa*, which was situated near China, and also *Suvarṇadvīpa* and *Ratnadvīpa* [6]. We come across few interesting geographical names in other books, including *Madanpura* of *Kamarupa*, mentioned in the ninth book.

Haribhadra's account of Jainism embodied in the works of our enquiry may be studied under the following heads:

The Tirthamkaras

The *Samaraiiccha Kahā* begins with the invocation to the Jaina *tīrtha m̄karas*. Paying homage to the first *tīrtha m̄karas*, Haribhadra says that *Ṛṣabhadeva* successfully resisted the arrows of the otherwise unconquerable cupid, that he (*Ṛṣabha*) was an abode of the *maṅgalas* of the three word, and that he attained the liberation [7]. Next he praises lord *Mahāvīra* who is called self born and lord of the Yogis [8]. Then he pay tributes the remaining 22 *tīrthamkaras*, saying that they attained freedom from the cycle of birth, oldage and death [9]. We are further informed that the speech and teachings of the *tīrthamkaras* found expressions in the form of 12 *aṅgas* [10] which are composed for the benefit and welfare of all [11]. The *tīrthamkaras* also thoroughly exposed the right intuition or perception (*samyakdarsana*), right knowledge (*samyakjnāna*) and right conduct (*samyakcaritra*) [12]. The trinity of tenets (*triratna*) is the destroyer of all evils and a precious jewel like *cintāmani* [13]. Haribhadra adds

that only that religion is benefactor and giver of happiness which has been preached by the *tīrthamkaras*, there words never mean otherwise.

Śrāvaka dharma

Haribhadra in his book also discusses the duties of the *śrāvakas* or the lay person. According to Haribhadra, a Jain house holder should observe twelve vows consisting of five *anuvratas*, three *guṇavratas*, and four *sikṣāvratas* [14]. Elucidating this he observes that there are five sins namely, violence, untruthfulness, theft, sexual intercourse and possessions. Vows for freedom for these sins are called *vratas*. Their partial adoption is *anuvrata* and total adoption is known as *mahāvratas* [15]. On account of the basic handicap that a householder cannot obtain *mokṣa*, *gārhasthya dharma* has been held in very low esteem by the Jaina thinkers. Haribhadra holds that the life of a householder has faggots in the form of numerous bodies; it burns with anger and several other evils and is fanned with the wind of ignorance. He compares worldly live (that a life of a householder) to a forest path infested with wild beats that is difficulties and dangers. In his opinion, religion (of the Jainas) cannot be acquired by those whose inflow of actions is not turned back. And the turning back of the inflow of actions is not possible for those who live the life of a householder. Thus the effect of the life of a householder are terrible, hence it should be abandoned by all. These observations expressly uphold the attainment of *mokṣa* as the sole aim of a true Jaina which a householder cannot get. The Jaina thinkers discouraged *gārhasthyadharmā* and motivated people to opt for asceticism. But this approach was obviously impracticable, for the existence of any society without householder is inconceivable [16]. As the real spiritual discipline starts from the practice of the lesser vows whereas the supra-moral stage comes last. Haribhadra's contribution consists in giving recognition even to common-sense morality which he rightly calls *lokadharmā*[17].

Asceticism

Highlighting the importance of asceticism, Haribhadra makes the following observation:

This world is illusory like *indraajāla* (magic) and its end is not happy. Hence, those who desert the *gārhasthya dharma* and opt for a life of a muni and praiseworthy and deserve to be emulated. Why is the man born on this earth and where has he to go herefrom? These fundamental questions together with the miseries of worldly life move a person to resort to the life of a *śramaṇa* which enables him to devote himself fully to find out there solutions. Haribhadra compares *pravrajyā* to a great axe (*mahākuthāra*) that cuts the tree of karma, sets a person free from all (worldly bonds) and enables him to reach heaven.

One who opted to the life of a *muni* was first initiated by a Jain *guru*. After being formally initiated, he studied scriptures and observe prescribed vows. Haribhadra lays down the following rules and vows for the Jaina ascetics: seeing the friend and foe alike, abstinence from telling lies observance of celibacy by mind, body and speech, detachment from foods and cloths, taking food during day time only, eating food in small quantities and at proper time, forbearance for hunger and thirst, sleeping on the ground, obedience to teachers and observance of internal as well as external austerities, observing forgiveness, softness, uprightness, self-control, purity, non-possession, ascetic attains, the states of tranquillity, and abstinence respectively [18]. These deeds enables one to attain *paramapada* i.e., *mokṣa*.

Haribhadra's theory of karma is based on the law of cause and effect, implying that everyone has to bear the consequences of his actions. He makes mentions of eight-fold actions [19]. As for the causes of these actions, Haribhadra enumerates *mithyādarśana* (false perception), *ajñāna* (ignorance), *avirati* (continuity), *pramāda* (lethargy or inactivity), *kaṣāya* (attachment of worldly object) and *Yoga* [20]. Haribhadra goes into the subtle details of these actions and sums up his observation in the following words:

The bondage of karma which is secured by the covers of knowledge (*jñānāvaraniya*), perception (*darśanāvaraniya*) and impediment (*antarāya*) and hatred (*dveṣa*) resulting from strong attachment can be loosened and rendered ineffective only with unlimited difficulty. A good action done by a moral person to an evil person also yields evil result [21].

Thus by annihilating the effects of accumulated the former deeds and preventing the process of their further accumulation one becomes free from the worldly bonds, attains the supreme position (*paramapada*) and enjoys internal bliss and beatitude [22].

Epilogue

In the end of this discussion we may observe that, through this work, Haribhadra establish *Mahārāṣṭri Prākṛit* as the intellectual language of Jainism. *Samaraiccha Kahā* fairly good account of several important doctrine of monasticism. Besides, we also get in it interesting descriptions of the rites, rituals, offerings etc. connected with Jainism. He was able to use his familiarity with the techniques of Brahminical learning to benefit Jainism by writing in the style of classical Brahminical scholarship. He is also noted for his respect of other religious traditions. However ultimately he supported Jainism and its different aspects of monasticism. His writings always have a fresh approach that investigates the merits and demerits with the object of propagation of knowledge. He studied thoroughly the works of his predecessors and systematically consolidated their thought.

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JAIN BHAWAN : ITS AIMS AND OBJECTS

Since the establishment of the Jain Bhawan in 1945 in the Burra Bazar area of Calcutta by eminent members of Jain Community, the Jain Bhawan has kept the stream of Jain philosophy and religion flowing steadily in eastern India for the last over fiftyeight years. The objectives of this institution are the following:

1. To establish the greatness of Jainism in the world rationally and to spread its glory in the light of new knowledge.
2. To develop intellectual, moral and literary pursuits in the society.
3. To impart lessons on Jainism among the people of the country.
4. To encourage research on Jain Religion and Philosophy.

To achieve these goals, the Jain Bhawan runs the following programmes in various fields.

1. School:

To spread the light of education the Bhawan runs a school, the Jain Shikshalaya, which imparts education to students in accordance with the syllabi prescribed by the West Bengal Board. Moral education forms a necessary part of the curricula followed by the school. It has on its roll about 550 students and 25 teachers.

2. Vocational and Physical Classes:

Accepting the demands of the modern times and the need to equip the students to face the world suitably, it conducts vocational and physical activity classes. Classes on traditional crafts like tailoring, stitching and embroidery and other fine arts along with Judo, Karate and Yoga are run throughout the year, not just for its own students, but for outsiders as well. They are very popular amongst the ladies of Burra Bazar of Calcutta.

3. Library:

“Education and knowledge are at the core of all round the development of an individual. Hence the pursuit of these should be the sole aim of life”. Keeping this philosophy in mind a library was established on the premises of the Bhawan, with more than 10,000 books on Jainism, its literature and philosophy and about 3,000 rare manuscripts, the library is truly a treasure trove. A list of such books and manuscripts can be obtained from the library.

4. Periodicals and Journals:

To keep the members abreast of contemporary thinking in the field of religion the library subscribes to about 100 (one hundred) quarterly, monthly and weekly periodicals from different parts of the world. These can be issued to members interested in the study of Jainism.

5. Journals:

Realising that there is a need for reasearch on Jainism and that scholarly knowledge needs to be made public, the Bhawan in its role as a research institution brings out three periodicals: *Jain Journal* in English, *Titthayara* in Hindi and *Śramaṇa* in Bengali. In 37 years of its publication, the Jain Journal has carved out a *niche* for itself in the field and has received universal acclaim. The Bengali journal *Śramaṇa*, which is being published for thirty year, has become a prominent channel for the sbvgftr54pread of Jain philosophy in West Bengal. This is the only Journal in Bengali which deals exclusively with matters concerning any aspects of Jainism. Both the Journals are edited by a